

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF WOVEN FABRIC CARBON/MAGNESIUM-COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The mechanical behaviour of a woven fabric carbon/magnesium-composite which is manufactured by a gas pressure infiltration technique is the subject of this research work. Apart from the investigation of the influence of the fibre volume content (50-70 vol.-%) on the bending strength, all other mechanical testing (bending, tensile and compression test) is carried out by using composites with a constant fibre volume fraction of about 60 vol.-%. The main points of the mechanical characterisations are the orientation and temperature dependence, as well as the thermal long term stability of the 0/90° woven fabric C/Mg-composites. The investigated two-dimensionally reinforced magnesium composites show a typical orthotropic mechanical behaviour. The 0/90° strength is temperature independent up to 300°C. Moreover, the outstanding mechanical properties stay unchanged even after a long thermal exposure (200°C; 1000h).

KEYWORDS: Woven fabric composite, carbon magnesium composite, MMC, mechanical properties, thermal stability, orientation influence, temperature influence.

INTRODUCTION

Continuously reinforced metal matrix composites have received significant attention in the last few years. Compared to conventional engineering materials they offer high specific stiffness and strength, tailored thermal expansion and conductivity. Especially the low density (1.8 g/cm³), as well as the remarkable in-axis tensile, fatigue strength and stiffness make unidirectionally carbon fibre reinforced magnesium (C/Mg) extremely attractive for advanced aerospace and automotive applications [1-5]. However, C/Mg-composites have particularly poor off-axis properties [4,6]. Fibre coatings and adapted fibre/alloy systems are able to reduce the anisotropic behaviour of the composites slightly [6-8]. A much more effective way to surmount this specific weakness, which is pursued in the present paper, is to use two-dimensional (2D-) woven fabrics. The results reported in this paper are part of a more comprehensive study with different C/Mg-systems [9].

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The specific subject of this research work is the AM20/T300J-composite system, which is manufactured by a gas pressure melt infiltration technique [9, 10].

A magnesium matrix with 2 wt.-% aluminium (AM20: 2 wt.-% Al, 0.6 wt.-% Mn, balance Mg [11]) was chosen because of the comparatively moderate fibre/matrix-reaction (Al_4C_3) resulting in an optimised interfacial strength [8, 12]. The commercial 2D satin 1/4 woven fabrics are made of the high-tenacity carbon fibre T300J produced by Toray. The woven fabric shows 7 filaments per cm in warp and fill direction and weigh 285 g/m². The fibre preforms were manufactured without binder by stacking several woven fabric sheets (typically 180x80 mm²) in the infiltration form. Depending on the desired fibre volume fraction a certain amount of woven fabric layers, which can be calculated by Eqn.1, was used.

$$V_F = \frac{d^2 \pi N_L N_F x}{2h} 100\% \quad (1)$$

with:

V_F :	Fibre volume fraction
d :	Fibre diameter (here: $d=7.1\mu\text{m}$)
N_L :	Amount of woven fabric layers
N_F :	Fibres per filament (here: $N_F=3000$)
x :	Filaments per cm
h :	Thickness of the composite plate

Mechanical testing

The mechanical characterisation including bending, tensile and compression tests was performed with an 100kN Instron 4505 machine.

The bending strength specimens had the dimensions of 100x10x2 mm³ and were tested corresponding the German standard DIN 29971. According to this test method the influence of the following factors on the bending strength were examined:

- Fibre volume fraction
- Orientation of the fibres
- Temperature in the range of room temperature to 400°C
- Isothermal exposure at 200°C and a duration of 1h to 1000h

The composite 0/90° tensile strength was determined by using flat specimens with a total length of 175 mm. The gage length was 50 mm with a cross section of 8x2 mm². The ±45° tensile samples had no gage length and a dimension of 100x10x2 mm³. All tensile tests were performed at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min.

The compression strength was measured according to the German standard DIN 50106 for unreinforced metals. The cylindrical specimens had a diameter of 6 mm and height of 9 mm. For comparison the Celanese compression test method [13] with flat specimens of 112 mm in length and a cross section of 6.3x2 mm² were used. For both methods the crosshead speed was 0.5 mm/min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Influence of the fibre volume content on the bending strength of 2D-AM20/T300J

The influence of the fibre volume fraction on the bending strength and stiffness can be seen in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Influence of the fibre content on the 0/90°-bending strength and stiffness of 2D-AM20/T300J composites

According to the Rule of Mixture both the 0/90°-bending strength and stiffness show approximately a linear dependence of the fibre volume content in the range of 50-70 vol.-%. Large variations of the bending strength with about 70 vol.-% can be observed. However stable mechanical properties are obtained at volume fractions below 60 vol.-%. Therefore all further mechanical composite testing are carried out with a constant moderate fibre volume fraction of about 57 vol.-%.

Orientation dependence on mechanical properties of 2D-woven fabric reinforced magnesium

As seen in Fig. 2, the two-dimensionally reinforced magnesium composites show a typical orthotropic mechanical behaviour which has been previously observed with other woven fabric composites [14]. Both the tensile and the bending strength reach the highest values in the 0° and 90°, respectively the fill and the warp direction. The total tensile strain at composite fracture does not exceed 1%. In contrast to the 0/90° response, the woven fabric reinforced composite show much lower strength in the $\pm 45^\circ$ direction. Bending and tensile strength reach a minimum. The tensile strength is just slightly higher than the unreinforced matrix AM20. The total fracture strain of the $\pm 45^\circ$ composite samples is about 5% and half as big as the unreinforced matrix. The $\pm 45^\circ$ tensile test specimens show shear failure, i.e. the crack surface is parallel to fibre orientation. The 0/90° tensile specimens fail normal to the loading direction.

To analyse the orientation dependence of the compression strength of the 2D-AM20/T300J two types of fibre orientations are tested: Load direction perpendicular (Fig. 3a) and parallel (Fig. 3b) to the woven fabric layers.

Figure 2: The orthotropic mechanical behaviour of 0/90°-reinforced AM20/T300J composites (57 vol.-% fibre content) in comparison to isotropic tensile behaviour of the unreinforced matrix AM20

Table 1: Influence of the fibre orientation on the compression strength of 2D-AM20/T300J (57 vol.-% fibre content)

Fibre orientation (related to the compression direction)	Compression strength [MPa]
0/90° parallel	505 ± 84
perpendicular	583 ± 48
unreinforced	225 [7]

As Table 1 indicates, the compression strength of the composite is more than twice as high as that of the unreinforced AM20, whereas the difference between loading the composite perpendicular and the parallel to the fibre orientation is rather small. However, both fracture modes can be clearly distinguished, as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Influence of the fibre orientation on the fracture mode of the compression specimens. The white arrows are pointing out the shear and delamination cracks

With an orientation of the woven fabric laminates perpendicular to the compression direction only shear failure in the plane of the maximum shear stress can be seen (Fig. 3a). The compression specimen loaded parallel to the fibre direction demonstrates a different behaviour (Fig. 3b): Beside the shear-cracks additional delamination cracks parallel to the woven fabric layers occur. This is the reason why the attained compression strength is somewhat smaller. Compared to these results the Celanese compression test method of the 0/90°-bending strength parallel to the laminates showed without exception a slightly higher strength of about 580 MPa instead of 505 MPa.

Mechanical properties at elevated temperatures and after thermal exposure

Fig. 4 illustrates the temperature influence on the mechanical behaviour of 0/90°-reinforced AM20/T300J in comparison to unreinforced AM20.

Figure 4: The influence of the temperature on the mechanical behaviour of 0/90°-reinforced AM20/T300J

Regarding the low fibre volume content of only half of 57 vol.-% in loading direction outstanding bending and tensile strength can be achieved even at elevated temperatures. In contrast to unreinforced AM20, which tensile strength decreases distinctly with increasing temperatures, the composite strength is constant up to 300°C. Only at higher temperatures (e.g. 400°C) the strength declines and the composite strength will not be longer determined by the fibre/matrix interface strength but by the very low matrix strength itself [9].

In contrast to many other magnesium matrix composites with e.g. alumina short-fibres [15] the excellent 2D-AM20/T300J-composite strength still exist even after long thermal exposure, as one can see in Fig 5.

Compared to the as-cast specimens neither the bending strength nor the bending stiffness is reduced. The main reason for this excellent thermal stability is that carbon and magnesium is thermodynamical inert (the Gibb's enthalpy values ΔG^0 for the formation of magnesium carbides MgC_2 and Mg_2C_3 are positive from casting to room temperature) [16] and that the

moderate reaction between the alloying element aluminium and the carbon fibre is completed during the composite processing.

Figure 5: The influence of the thermal exposure duration at 200°C on the bending strength and stiffness of woven fabric reinforced AM20/T300J

Comparison of the temperature influence on the composite strength of different woven fabric reinforced composite

Fig. 6 gives a comparison of the temperature influence on the bending strength of different woven fabric reinforced composites. All composites are reinforced with woven fabric made of high tenacity carbon fibres with similar fibre strength. The fibre volume content of all composites is approximately 60 vol.-%.

Figure 6: Comparison of the temperature influence on the bending strength of different woven fabric reinforced composites [17, 18]

At low temperatures (up to 100°C) the C/EP-system (carbon fibre reinforced epoxy) shows the highest bending strength whereas these properties get quickly lost at elevated temperatures [17]. In contrast, the strength of C/C composites (carbon fibre reinforced carbon) is relatively low at room temperature but increases slightly up to temperatures of 2000°C in a non-oxidising atmosphere [18]. However, the woven fabric reinforced AM20/T300J shows

medium strength at room temperature, but has superior properties in the temperature range of 180°C to 400°C. Therefore, the 2D-AM20/T300J-system is able to close the strength gap between C/EP and C/C-composites and makes C/Mg-composites extremely attractive for the internal combustion engine and other high temperature components. Some near-net-shape cast prototypes of woven fabric reinforced AM20/T300J are shown in Fig.7:

Figure 7: Woven fabric reinforced AM20/T300J-prototypes manufactured at the university of Erlangen

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the present investigation lead to the following conclusions:

1. Strength and stiffness of 0/90° AM20/T300J increase linearly with the fibre volume fraction.
2. The 0/90°-reinforced AM20/T300J system shows an orthotropic mechanical behaviour. The 0/90°-tensile strength is more than three times higher than unreinforced AM20. The tensile strength with $\pm 45^\circ$ fibre orientation is only slightly higher than the unreinforced matrix.
3. Bending and tensile strength of 0/90° reinforced AM20/T300J is constant up to 300°C. The composite system shows an excellent thermal stability even after long thermal exposure (200°C, 1000h).
4. Compared to other woven fabric reinforced composites (C/EP and C/C) the discussed C/Mg-system has superior strength in the temperature range of 180°C to 400°C. Therefore 2D-AM20/T300J-system is a very promising material for high temperature composites as required in internal combustion engines.

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